

ANALYSIS OF CYBERCRIMES DETECTION METHODS IN DIGITAL FORENSICS WITH OPEN SOURCE

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Abstract. *The article presents information regarding the analysis of the methods and means of committing cybercrimes and a description of the requirements for collecting digital evidence, as well as a detailed explanation of the problems that arise when collecting digital evidence in digital forensics and ways to solve them.*

Keywords: *digital forensics, digital traces, EnCase, Message Digest 5 (MD5), SHA256.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that studying the statistics of computer crime investigations today, we can conclude that the most commonly used tools for committing cybercrimes are software and hardware. It should be noted that the choice of means for committing a crime by a cybercriminal is directly related to his goal and motive, which are the psychological basis for the behavior of any person.

Literary analysis and methodology.

According to the source of origin, the means of computer crimes can be divided into ready-made, modified and proprietary means.

It is known to everyone that cybercriminals can use ready-made or modified software, as well as their own tools. This is most typical for high-tech methods of committing computer crimes, which use computer programs created by gang members or third-party experts commissioned by criminals.

According to the technology of use, the means of computer crimes can be divided into remote access and non-remote access [1].

Currently, in most cases, computer crimes are committed by remote access through telecommunications networks using conventional computer equipment with special software installed. This fundamental situation has important implications for both the investigation and prevention of computer crimes.

Definitely, using remote access malware via information networks allows crimes to be committed against entire computer systems simultaneously. With such access, criminals do not need to penetrate the premises where the target is located, and the attackers do not leave so-called "digital traces". A digital trace is always the result of the performance and impact of computer programs.

According to the technical content, the means under consideration can be divided, with a certain degree of conventionality, into hardware, software and embedded.

Moreover, digital forensics is a scientific and technical process associated with the search, identification, research, documentation and analysis of digital evidence. This evidence is then used in legal proceedings or internal investigations. Digital forensics specialists have a wide range of knowledge and skills, such as the technical aspects of information technology, the ability to work with various software and hardware, and an understanding of the legal aspects of the process. Digital forensics is an area in which many tools are used that support various stages of work. Here are some main categories, including examples of such tools:

- Evidence collection: This is the first step in a forensic scientist's work, where digital evidence is found, extracted, and stored. FTK Imager is an example of tools that perform these tasks. It is used to create clear images of a hard drive without the possibility of changing them. This is important to eliminate the possibility of data corruption. And the Cellebrite tool is widely used by law enforcement to obtain data from mobile devices, including remote ones.

- Evidence Analysis: The tools in this category will help you analyze the collected data and perform advanced searches. An example of this is the EnCase tool for these tasks. It is one of the leading tools for data analysis and verification. It provides data analysis across multiple platforms using EnCase. Autopsy is one such tool. It is a free and open-source tool that offers a complete set of features for detailed analysis.

- Data Recovery: Data recovery tools are essential for recovering deleted, corrupted, or otherwise inaccessible data. Recuva can be used to perform these tasks. It is a free tool that can recover accidentally deleted files. R-Studio can even recover data from corrupted or formatted drives.

- Network Analysis: These tools allow you to analyze network traffic and monitor the interactions between different devices. An example of a tool is Wireshark. It is the gold standard for network traffic packet analysis, allowing you to study network communications in detail. NetworkMiner helps visualize network communication and makes analysis easier.

- Malware Analysis: The tools in this category allow forensic experts to analyze malware to understand its functionality and potential impact on the system. VirusTotal can be used as an example for these tasks. This online service allows you to scan files for viruses using various antivirus engines. IDA Pro software is used for binary code analysis and reverse engineering. Ghidra, developed by the NSA, is a free decompiler and reverse engineering tool that helps analyze malicious code.

- Security and Data Analysis: These tools provide security, protection, and analysis of digital evidence. An example of a tool is VeraCrypt, which can be used to encrypt data. GnuPG can also be used to perform similar operations.

- Scripting and Automation: Using scripting languages such as Python or Bash to automate routine tasks and create custom tools for specific needs.

It is worth mentioning that each set of tools depends on the specific task and the preferences of the specialist. In addition, digital forensics is constantly evolving, new tools and methods are emerging, so professionals need to constantly conduct research and provide a new set of tools. There are three main data collection methods that can be used to copy data from a suspicious system to a trusted system:

The network can be used to copy data from the suspect computer system to a designated server. In this case, you can use network communication tools such as Netcat. Alternatively, you can mount a network drive and copy the data to the server. Mounting storage devices such as

network shares, CD drives, and hard drives allows you to access files through the computer's file system.

However, a suspect storage device such as a hard drive can be removed from the suspect system and connected to a trusted server to access the data.

A new hard drive may have been connected or installed on the suspect system. The suspect system can boot from a trusted USB stick or CD and finally create an image of the suspect drive on the new drive.

SATA, SCSI, or IDE drives are used to collect evidence from the device.

It is recommended to power off the system under test and boot it onto a trusted computer system that is used for testing. Alternatively, the hard drive can be removed and connected to the forensic system.

However, in some cases it is recommended to turn on the machine under test to collect all the data needed for the test from active memory, since turning off the system may result in the loss of all data from memory cells. Here are seven recommended steps for implementing a blacklist:

- Step 1: Here the suspicious system is unlocked to allow tracking of records and registration of the establishment of a time stamp, after which no further changes will occur in the system [5].

- Step 2. Remove the user from the suspect system to ensure that the chain of custody is created and complete. When, by whom, where the evidence was received, where it was stored and who officed or owned it at the time of receipt [3].

- Step 3. Check secondary media and remove any remaining media such as floppy disks and zip disks. Each device should have a chain of custody [1].

- Step 4: Record the Unified Extensible Firmware Interface (UEFI) and Basic Input/Output System (BIOS) information. There is no need to load a system file to check the BIOS or UEFI information. The UEFI or BIOS information should be automatically generated in the form of a storage chain. The BIOS or UEFI information collected is about the state of the system time and data. The BIOS or system time is important if it may differ from the actual clock yoga set for your geographic region [8].

- Step 5: Enable the imaging driver. This is the most dangerous part of the evidence collection process. You must be careful not to overwrite the original media every time you access it. I have not used a disk to store images before, but I always need to use some software to clear pre-written files on the disk [3].

- Step 6: After creating an image of the suspect user, a cryptographic hash generated by the program is written to create the image. This can be message digest 5 (MD5), SHA256, etc. The cryptographic hash ensures data integrity [5].

- Step 7: Finally, pack and label the evidence, then label the disc with edible medical treatment and store it in a place inaccessible to unauthorized persons [1].

It is not a secret that in the modern world, the number of electronic documents stored both on computers and in cloud services is increasing every day. At the moment, the need to use electronic digital documents in legal activities, as well as electronic digital evidence in legal proceedings is natural. In legal proceedings in a digital society, digital evidence is an important tool for proving the facts and circumstances of a case, especially in cases where traditional evidence, such as paper documents or witnesses, is unavailable. Therefore, the problems of collecting, researching and using electronic digital evidence are relevant and important for the

modern legal community and require further research and development in this area. The use of such documents as evidence may encounter a number of problems related to the authenticity, integrity, safety and confidentiality of these documents. It is known that an electronic document must have the following characteristics: - authenticity - a feature that guarantees the identity of an electronic document to a published document;

- reliability, a property of an electronic document, the content of which is a complete and correct representation of the transactions, actions or facts under investigation and which can be trusted in subsequent transactions or subsequent actions;

- integrity, the state of an electronic document that has not changed since its creation;

- usability is a property of an electronic document that allows it to be localized and reproduced at any time.

Besides that, the electronic document is considered equivalent to a paper document if it is signed with an electronic signature or other analogue of a handwritten signature. Electronic digital evidence is information received in electronic form that confirms the facts and circumstances associated with the work. This may be electronic documents, electronic messages, conversation recordings, video and audio recordings, photographs and other materials received in electronic form.

Additionally, unlike traditional evidence, an electronic document as evidence has a complex structure, and it cannot be argued that it must include both electronic digital content and the ability to update. It is necessary to dwell on some of the current problems of the issue under study.

The first problem, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of collecting and storing digital evidence. A special feature of this evidence is its electronic form, which, despite all security measures, can be changed and forged, which can affect its reliability and authenticity. Therefore, the collection and storage of electronic digital evidence requires special attention and compliance with certain rules. These rules primarily include:

- Use of special programs. Collection and storage of electronic digital evidence requires the use of special software that allows storing evidence in a safe and secure form.

- Maintain the integrity of evidence, electronic digital evidence must be stored in its original form without changes. For this purpose, special hash sums and digital signatures are used, which allow you to verify the authenticity of evidence and track any changes.

- Protection from unauthorized access, for protecting electronic digital evidence from unauthorized access, passwords, encryption and other modern data protection methods should be used.

- Storage of metadata, in addition to the content of electronic digital evidence, it is necessary to store metadata, including information about the date of creation, modification, author, etc.

- Compliance with legal requirements, the collection and storage of electronic digital evidence must comply with the requirements of the legislation and regulations governing this area.

The second problem, it is necessary to develop an effective technology for collecting and searching electronic digital evidence.

Moreover, data collection and storage procedures are an important step in the use of electronic digital evidence. They may vary depending on the type of data and the means used for collection and storage [4].

However, data collection can be carried out through active intervention (e.g. collecting data from an electronic device) or passive collection (e.g. collecting data from social networks). It should be taken into account that there is a risk of destruction or modification of data during active intervention, so special programs and technologies should be used to save data in their original form.

It is worth mentioning that data preservation is also an important procedure, since it guarantees the safety of evidence until it is used in the process. Various means can be used to store data, such as external hard drives, cloud storage, servers, etc. It is also important to protect data from unauthorized access, including through the use of passwords, encryption and other data protection technologies. In general, the procedures for collecting and storing electronic digital evidence require specialized knowledge and skills in the field of information technology and cybersecurity. Compliance with the rules and regulations established by law when collecting and storing such information will prevent possible errors and improper behavior, and will ensure the legality of the use of digital evidence in future legal proceedings.

The collection and analysis of electronic digital evidence requires the use of special tools. Data collection and analysis tools, especially for large-scale electronic data processing, include:

- computer software for data collection: this software allows you to collect data from various sources, such as computers, mobile devices, servers, and cloud storage;
- tools for physical removal of disks and storage media: such tools allow you to delete data from physical storage media such as hard drives, flash drives, CD/DVD, etc.;
- special programs for data analysis: such programs allow you to analyze and process data, determine relationships and correlations between data, and create graphs and charts;
- data recovery tools: such tools are used in cases of data damage or deletion and allow you to recover lost data;
- data protection tools: such tools allow you to protect data from unauthorized access and modification, as well as ensure its safety and integrity.

Third problem, there is an urgent need to form and recognize an independent relevant area of knowledge, a unique scientific basis for working with electronic digital evidence. Currently, the collection, storage, protection and use of electronic digital evidence have given rise to such an area of scientific and legal knowledge as digital forensics. Digital forensics is the field of knowledge, methods and technologies used to collect, analyze, interpret and present digital evidence in criminal and civil proceedings. In forensic literature, digital criminology is more closely related to criminal proceedings and is defined as a new system of knowledge in forensics based on an understanding of the operation of modern information and communication technologies and used to identify patterns of criminal significance:

- criminal activity aimed at interfering with the normal functioning of information systems, their components, or actions aimed at using them as a tool for committing other crimes;
- creation, modification, transfer, destruction of information related to the preparation, commission, concealment of crimes, on electronic media, in information and telecommunication networks, virtual space;
- collection of digital information through the implementation of technical procedures that ensure its legal significance;
- study of digital information stored in individual information objects, as well as in an electronic information storage environment;

- evaluation of the obtained results, linking them with the actions of the subject and using them to qualify the criminal act;
- integration of digital evidence into the existing system of evidence in accordance with the procedural form of their receipt" [3].

But it is difficult to overestimate the importance of digital evidence in legal disputes in civil and arbitration proceedings. The developments of criminologists are undoubtedly in demand and necessary. In such legal proceedings, popular forensic medical assistance can provide real and important information. The content of digital forensics should include aspects such as data collection (collecting and storing electronic data from digital devices and other sources); data analysis: methods and tools for processing and interpreting digital evidence, including searching, analyzing and classifying data; identification (determining the authorship and authenticity of digital evidence); event reconstruction (using digital data to reconstruct the sequence of events); protecting digital evidence from unauthorized access and modification (electronic security); verifying numerical data and presenting test results.

Overall, digital forensics is an important area of activity for judicial and law enforcement agencies, as well as for any organization dealing with the security of digital data and information.

The next issue to be addressed is the use of digital evidence in legal proceedings. Electronic digital evidence can be of great value in legal cases, but it may face various limitations and challenges.

The procedures for presenting digital evidence to the court include several stages aimed at ensuring its admissibility and reliability:

1. Identification and authentication of evidence, it is necessary to determine the source and authenticity of digital evidence, as well as to verify its integrity and authenticity.
2. Preparation of evidence, digital evidence must be preserved in its original form and with metadata containing information about the time of creation, modification and other parameters.
3. Presentation of evidence, digital evidence can be presented to the court both in the form of electronic documents and in the form of paper copies. It is important to ensure that they are legible and complete.
4. Proof of authenticity, it is necessary to prove the authenticity of digital evidence, for example, by involving an expert who can conduct an examination and issue an opinion on the authenticity of the evidence.
5. Admissibility, it is important to convince the court that the digital evidence is based on relevant laws and regulations, as well as on the practice of their use in similar cases.

It is important to suggest that one of the limitations of using electronic digital evidence in court proceedings is its technical complexity and the possibility of forgery. For ensuring its admissibility and reliability, it is necessary to conduct special examinations and investigations, which can lead to an increase in the time and cost of the trial. It is important to note that access to information contained in digital evidence can be problematic due to privacy and data protection restrictions.

Electronic evidence examiners must have certain credentials to perform their duties in court cases. They must have knowledge of digital forensics, software, computer networks and operating systems to analyse, collect and present digital evidence.

In addition, examinees must be aware of the legal rules governing the use of electronic evidence, including privacy and cybersecurity laws. They must be familiar with the procedures

used in courts and be able to present their findings in a way that is understandable to the court and the parties involved in the case.

However, the credentials of electronic evidence examiners may be limited, for example, due to rapidly changing technology, the difficulty of recovering deleted data or the fact that the data is encrypted. Conflict of interest issues may also arise when parties may attempt to challenge the experts' opinions or argue about which examination method should be used. The use of electronic digital evidence in court proceedings may raise a number of complexities related to its collection, analysis, presentation and evaluation. Some of these issues are listed below:

- **Technical Issues:** Working with electronic digital evidence may present technical issues related to storing, transmitting, retrieving and analyzing data.

- **Access to Data:** Collecting electronic evidence may require specialized skills and technology. In addition, access to information may require court permission.

- **Data Reliability:** Electronic data may be corrupted, which may affect its reliability and validity.

- **Data Complexity:** Electronic data can be very large and complex, making it difficult to analyze and use in court proceedings.

- **Insufficient Skills of Participants in the Process,** working with electronic evidence requires specialized knowledge and skills that not all participants in the process possess.

- **Lack of Legal Standards:** Unlike traditional evidence, digital evidence is a relatively new phenomenon, and the rules governing its use may be unclear or inadequate.

- **Privacy issues:** While working with electronic data, privacy issues arise related to the protection of personal information and commercial secrets.

Results. Thus, it can be concluded that the above problems and difficulties can significantly complicate the process of using electronic digital evidence in court proceedings and require careful preparation and appropriate precautions.

Some possible ways to overcome the difficulties associated with the use of digital evidence in court may include:

1. Organizing specialized departments and expert groups to process and analyze electronic data collected in criminal cases.

2. Developing more accurate and reliable methods for examining electronic data that can be used in judicial practice.

3. Ensuring a high level of data protection and confidentiality when using electronic digital evidence in court proceedings.

4. Improving the skills of judges and other participants in the judicial process in the field of digital forensics and the use of electronic digital evidence.

5. Developing and implementing modern technologies that allow for more efficient processing and analysis of large volumes of data, as well as ensuring their safety and reliability.

6. Strengthening cooperation between various public and private organizations dealing with digital crime and information security.

In conclusion, it can be suggested that such evidence has become an integral part of modern judicial practice. This requires the development of effective technologies for collecting, storing and analyzing electronic data. Although the use of electronic evidence in court proceedings has many advantages, there are also some problems associated with its use. However, the development of digital forensics and the use of new technologies in this area make it possible to

effectively solve emerging problems. In general, the use of digital evidence in court proceedings contributes to the effectiveness of justice and the safety of citizens. At the same time, for further development of this area, more attention should be paid to the development of new technologies, improving the procedures for electronic collection and analysis of data.

REFERENCES

1. Tashev K.A., Fayzieva D.S., Yuldasheva N.S., "Modeling a Speaker by Preliminary Processing of Speech Signals" International Scientific Journal "Science and Innovation" Volume 2 Issue October 10, 2023 uif-2022: 8.2 | numbers: 2181-3337 | scientists.uz.
2. Akbarov D.E. "Cryptographic Methods of Ensuring Information Security and Their Application" - Tashkent, 2012. – P.394
3. Ganiev S.K., Karimov M.M., Toshev K.A. Information Security. 2016.
4. V.F. Shan'gin, Information Security and Information Protection, Moscow, Publishing House "Forum" - Infra-M, 2017.
5. Novitsky, V.A., Novitskaya, L.Yu. Concept and Types of Digital Evidence // Leningrad Journal. 2019. N. 1(55).
6. Samotuga A.E. Recognition of Subjects and Their Psychophysiological States Based on Signature Parameters to Protect Document Management: Diss. Cand. Tech. Sci. (Tech.) Omsk, 2017, P.124.
7. Yakovlev A.N. Digital Forensics and Its Importance for Investigating Crimes in the Modern Information Society // Improving Investigative Activities in the Context of Informatization: Collection of Materials of the International Scientific and Practical Conf. Minsk, April 12-13, 2018 / Investigative Committee of the Republic of Belarus; editor's office: